

COMMENTS ON CERTAIN CALCULATIONS IN "GENERAL RELATIVISTIC APPROACH TO THE VIS-VIVA EQUATION ON SCHWARZSCHILD METRIC"

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ABSTRACT. In this brief note, we conduct a detailed recheck on the theoretical derivations presented in the paper "General Relativistic Approach to the Vis-Viva Equation on Schwarzschild Metric" (arXiv:2404.10302). Several fundamental miscalculations and typographical errors are identified, such as inconsistent physical dimensions and algebraic mistakes in angular momentum derivation. With these errors revised, we demonstrate that the main conclusions of the original work are still credible. Furthermore, we provide the corrected formulae and complete derivation steps, which facilitate a clearer comprehension of the derivation and physical interpretation of the vis-viva equation in Schwarzschild spacetime.

The vis-viva equation plays a vital role in celestial mechanics. The classical vis-viva equation is derived entirely from Newton's law of universal gravitation, and thus fails to accurately predict the motion of celestial objects in strong gravitational fields. Accordingly, deriving modified forms of the vis-viva equation for orbital motion around various strong gravitational sources is of great significance for modern physical and astronomical observations. We conduct a detailed recheck on the theoretical derivations presented in the paper "General Relativistic Approach to the Vis-Viva Equation on Schwarzschild Metric" (arXiv:2404.10302) [2]. Several fundamental miscalculations and typographical errors are identified, such as inconsistent physical dimensions and algebraic mistakes in angular momentum derivation. With these errors revised, we demonstrate that the main conclusions of the original work are still credible.

The first suggestion for improvement in calculations in the paper appears in the line element of the Schwarzschild metric, where a factor of c^2 is missing in the coordinate time term. It is evident that the SI unit system is employed in the manuscript. Thus, uniform units should be maintained consistently throughout all derivations and expressions. This leads to dimensional inconsistencies in some of the subsequent formulas. The correct line element should be written as [3]:

$$(1) \quad ds^2 = -\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right)c^2 dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2.$$

In the equatorial plane ($\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$ and $\dot{\theta} = 0$), the line element of the Schwarzschild metric can be simplified as:

$$(2) \quad ds^2 = -\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right)c^2 dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2 d\phi^2.$$

The 4-velocity in this case is:

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$$(3) \quad u^2 = -\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right)c^2 \dot{t}^2 + \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right)^{-1} \dot{r}^2 + r^2 \dot{\phi}^2.$$

The Lagrangian of the constructed system is[1]:

$$(4) \quad L = \frac{1}{2} \left[-f c^2 \dot{t}^2 + f^{-1} \dot{r}^2 + r^2 \dot{\phi}^2 \right],$$

where $f = f(r) = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right)$. Thus, using the symmetry of the Lagrangian with respect to t and ϕ , we obtain:

$$(5) \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{t}} = -f c^2 \dot{t} = E,$$

$$(6) \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{\phi}} = r^2 \dot{\phi} = L_\phi.$$

Thus we can also obtain:

$$(7) \quad \dot{t} = -\frac{E}{f c^2},$$

$$(8) \quad \dot{\phi} = \frac{L_\phi}{r^2}.$$

It can be derived that:

$$(9) \quad \frac{E^2}{c^2} = f \left(c^2 + \frac{L_\phi^2}{r^2} + f^{-1} \dot{r}^2 \right) = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right) \left(c^2 + \frac{L_\phi^2}{r^2} + f^{-1} \dot{r}^2 \right).$$

When a planet is at its aphelion ($r = r_a$) and perihelion ($r = r_p$), condition $\dot{r} = 0$ must hold. At this point, Equation (9) can be simplified to:

$$(10) \quad \frac{E^2}{c^2} = f \left(c^2 + \frac{L_\phi^2}{r^2} \right) = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right) \left(c^2 + \frac{L_\phi^2}{r^2} \right).$$

Energy is always conserved, so we can obtain:

$$(11) \quad \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r_a}\right) \left(c^2 + \frac{L_\phi^2}{r_a^2} \right) = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r_p}\right) \left(c^2 + \frac{L_\phi^2}{r_p^2} \right),$$

using the properties $r_a + r_p = 2a$ and $r_a \cdot r_p = a^2(1 - e^2)$, we can obtain:

$$(12) \quad L_\phi^2 = GMa(1 - e^2) \left[1 - \frac{GM}{ac^2} \frac{3 + e^2}{1 - e^2} \right]^{-1}.$$

There is a discrepancy between Equation (12) and the corresponding formula in the original paper. On the one hand, this difference stems from coefficient errors concerning c , which also originates from the inconsistent dimensions of the spacetime line element in the original work. On the other hand, it is attributed to the exponent of the bracket term, which is most likely caused by typographical mistakes or improper first-order approximation by the original author.

Furthermore, since energy is conserved at perihelion and aphelion, the average energy at these two positions remains constant [2]:

$$(13) \quad E^2 = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r_a}\right) c^2 \left(c^2 + \frac{L_\phi^2}{r_a^2}\right) + \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r_p}\right) c^2 \left(c^2 + \frac{L_\phi^2}{r_p^2}\right) \right],$$

where $r_s = \frac{2GM}{c^2}$. From this, the expression for energy is derived as:

$$(14) \quad E^2 = c^2 \left\{ c^2 - \frac{r_s c^2}{a(1-e^2)} + \frac{L_\phi^2(1+e^2)}{a^2(1-e^2)^2} \left[1 - \frac{r_s}{a} \frac{1+3e^2}{(1-e^2)(1+e^2)} \right] \right\}.$$

Substituting Equation (12) into Equation (14), we obtain:

$$(15) \quad \frac{E^2}{c^2} = c^2 - \frac{r_s c^2}{a(1-e^2)} + \frac{r_s c^2}{2a} \frac{1+e^2}{1-e^2} \left[\frac{1 - \frac{r_s}{a} \frac{1+3e^2}{(1-e^2)(1+e^2)}}{1 - \frac{r_s}{2a} \frac{3+e^2}{1-e^2}} \right].$$

Finally, rearranging this expression, we obtain:

$$(16) \quad \frac{E^2}{c^2} = c^2 - \frac{r_s c^2}{2a} \left[\frac{1 - \frac{2r_s}{a(1-e^2)}}{1 - \frac{r_s}{2a} \frac{3+e^2}{1-e^2}} \right].$$

Then from Equation (9), we can obtain the corresponding radial component $u(r)$ of the four-velocity:

$$(17) \quad u^2(r) = -c^2 + \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right)^{-1} E^2.$$

Substituting Equation (16) into Equation (17), we finally obtain the general relativistically corrected vis-viva equation for equatorial orbital motion of particles (celestial bodies) in Schwarzschild spacetime:

$$(18) \quad u^2 = c^2 \left\{ \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right)^{-1} \left[1 - \frac{r_s}{2a} \cdot \frac{1 - \frac{2r_s}{a(1-e^2)}}{1 - \frac{r_s}{2a} \frac{3+e^2}{1-e^2}} \right] - 1 \right\}.$$

With Equation (18) in hand, we can perform a simple verification following the method adopted in the original paper by calculating the escape velocity. For a particle that barely escapes, we have $a=0$. Substituting this into the above expression yields:

$$(19) \quad u_e^2 = \lim_{a \rightarrow \infty} c^2 \left\{ \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right)^{-1} \left[1 - \frac{r_s}{2a} \cdot \frac{1 - \frac{2r_s}{a(1-e^2)}}{1 - \frac{r_s(3+e^2)}{2a(1-e^2)}} \right] - 1 \right\},$$

$$u_e^2 = c^2 \left[\left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right)^{-1} - 1 \right],$$

$$(20) \quad u_e^2 = c^2 \left(\frac{r}{r_s} - 1 \right)^{-1},$$

$$(21) \quad u_e = c \left(\frac{r}{r_s} - 1 \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}}.$$

Performing first-order approximation on Equation (20), we obtain:

$$(22) \quad u_e = \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{r}} \left(1 + \frac{GM}{c^2 r} \right),$$

its zeroth-order approximation coincides with the classical mechanical escape velocity, while all higher-order corrections arise from general relativity in the Schwarzschild spacetime.

This work was initially inspired during my inquiry into recent advances in gravitational dynamics and celestial motion research, for supporting my high-school lectures on the law of universal gravitation. As a time-honored fundamental relation in classical mechanics, the vis-viva equation deserves profound investigation on its general relativistic correction. Owing to my limited computational proficiency, over two weeks of continuous algebraic derivation was required for me to arrive at the original paper's modified vis-viva equation on the Schwarzschild spacetime.

Nevertheless, the majority of celestial bodies and cosmic structures in the universe possess intrinsic spin angular momentum. The spacetime generated by a gravitational source with intrinsic spin is described by the Kerr spacetime. As mentioned at the end of the original manuscript, extending the vis-viva equation to the Kerr metric will substantially deepen our understanding of accretion dynamics and the formation mechanism of jets around such celestial objects, based on the modified vis-viva equation in Schwarzschild spacetime investigated in the original work. This extension will open up multiple promising avenues for future research. These studies will strongly promote both theoretical and practical comprehension of a broad spectrum of astrophysical phenomena, ranging from binary black hole dynamics to the complex orbital motion of stars surrounding supermassive black holes at galactic nuclei.

References

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